

Federated Digital Research Infrastructures (DRI) for the Arts and Humanities Communities

Insights into Communities and Digital Research Practices

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June 2026

1 Introduction

This report aims to reflect the collective voice of the Arts & Humanities (A&H) research communities advocating for access to Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) in ways that support their digital research workflows and data management practices. The (A&H) communities bring together researchers across three thematic areas broadly categorised by the A&H Research Council into: 1) Histories, Cultures and Heritage, 2) Creative and Performing Arts, as well as 3) Languages and Literature. The research in these areas is funded mainly by the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and supported by the Infrastructure for Digital Arts and Humanities ().

2 Digital Research Infrastructure Ecosystem in Arts and Humanities

The Arts and Humanities DRI landscape reflects both the priorities of UKRI-DRI and those of the communities who have extensive experience curating and managing large-scale data. These communities are heterogeneous, bringing together researchers, practitioners, and digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs).

One of the most visible components of this infrastructure is the **data services**, including the AHRC-funded data services. IDAH provisions for data services which cater for different disciplines and/or types of data, including the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo); the Archaeology Data Service (ADS); the Literary and Linguistic Data Service (LLDS); the British Library Research Repository; the Museum Data Service (MDS); the Heritage Science Data Service (HSDS); and the Enact Practice Research Data Service, which is under development.

Moreover, **software components**, such as code libraries and tools, have been built during the research process. The long-term maintenance of these software components remains a challenge, as cultures around software engineering, including version control, documentation, and long-term maintenance, are not well embedded in the community. These needs are currently being addressed by the scoping project *Toward a new CCP for Arts, Humanities, and Culture research (CCP-AHC)* [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], which advocates for better capturing

use cases and "lessons learned", as well as making infrastructure relevant to AHC research, and tools discoverable.

The use of DRI **hardware components** and high-performance computing systems within research methods varies across the community. In most cases, researchers use institutional DRI, and the number of researchers with A&H projects applying for access to DRI Tier 1 and 2 hardware components remains low. Initiatives such as the **Digital Skills in Arts and Humanities (DISKAH) Network** aim to broaden access by developing digital skills and promote use cases of DRI amongst A&H communities.

There are also various capacity-building, training frameworks and collaboration networks that support skills development, knowledge exchange, and community advocacy. IDAH engages with the A&H research and practice communities to improve skills and promote the overall culture around data, tools and software, for instance, through the **DataCulture** project.

Taking into account all these existing components and with the aim of developing federated access to them, the following sections explain the methodology for proposing an operational roadmap to address the requirements of the A&H community.

3 Methodology

The research conducted to establish the requirements of the A&H communities for federation involved a thorough review of established research and evidence published in relevant literature ([Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]; [Beavan, Piza, Rob, et al. 2025]; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025]; [Black et al. 2024]; [Collier and Hamilton 2025]; [De Roure et al. 2022]; [Evans et al. 2023]; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024]; [Jackson et al. 2023]; [McGillivray et al. 2020]; [Rodriguez Echavarria et al. 2022]; [Romanova et al. 2021]; [Ross et al. 2024]; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023]; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023]; [Taylor et al. 2022]; [UKRI 2022]; [Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022]).

These reports and publications were selected based on the authors' knowledge of the DRI landscape evolution in Arts and Humanities over the last few years, in parallel with or driven by the development and funding of the IDAH programme, as well as other community initiatives, notably the development of the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association. This literature was compiled and analysed thematically, highlighting insights from the A&H subdisciplines, as well as cross-disciplinary research, in terms of data practices, tools and workflows, collaboration and professional development.

It should also be emphasised that the Arts & Humanities (A&H) research communities are not a single, homogeneous group. Research needs vary considerably across subdisciplines and are further shaped by career stage, access to institutional infrastructure, collaborative contexts, and levels of digital skills. Acknowledging and addressing diverse requirements is therefore critical to ensure that a federated DRI is accessible, inclusive and equitable, and that it can effectively support the broad A&H research and practice communities.

4 Requirements from Literature Survey

4.1 Research Outputs, Datasets and Software

Communities use and produce heterogeneous datasets of varying complexities involving multiple formats, parts, sizes and data types. While textual data has the strongest representation, a large percentage of researchers work with multidimensional data, including born digital data (e.g. spatial, numerical, visual, audiovisual) and sensor data (real-time). The resulting datasets

are often well curated in accordance with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles, enabling the structuring and connecting of knowledge. Researchers also generate a range of software artefacts, particularly interactive applications, mobile apps, and server-side applications. Researchers and practitioners are interested in the use of DRI for the retention, use/reuse and preservation of these outputs.

- 4.1.1 DRI workflows should accommodate heterogeneous datasets with diverse data types, varied and evolving sizes, ensuring that processing pipelines, tools, and interfaces offer effective support ([De Roure et al. 2022]; [Rodriguez Echavarría et al. 2022]; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarría, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 4; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 38). File formats and sizes for workflows, such as migration, movement and emulation, should be recommended to the community ([Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.1.2 DRI should be capable of sustainably hosting and preserving complex, full-stack scholarly outputs (e.g., data, software, interfaces, documentation) ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 14).
- 4.1.3 DRI should embed copyright policy into technical workflows so that systems can automatically determine whether an asset can be shared, reused, or distributed. Intellectual Property Rights must be agreed via a governance mechanism, for instance, centrally and by data provider ([De Roure et al. 2022]).
- 4.1.4 DRI should support licensing for granular release of content, enabling researchers or data owners to specify conditions for access, downloading, and reuse on a per-request basis ([Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.1.5 DRI should support the adoption of a robust Data Management Plan (DMP) following best practices and clear data policies ([Taylor et al. 2022], p. 50; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], pp. 7, 9). Researchers require guidance on how software should be managed, documented, stored, maintained, and easily made accessible and findable, including beyond the funding period ([Romanova et al. 2021], pp. 40, 41; [Taylor et al. 2022], pp. 40, 41; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 63; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], pp. 1, 29).
- 4.1.6 DRI should support moving data via batch file transfers or other automated mechanisms. Long-lived or refreshable access tokens can support orchestration across systems ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 5).
- 4.1.7 DRI should support a minimum level of centralisation and integration for storing, analysing, and sharing data, while exploring the potential of decentralisation technologies ([Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], pp. 1, 12).

Communities prioritise sharing and enabling access to both data and software outputs. Once data are openly available on web platforms, interoperability is viewed as a key mechanism for connecting datasets across institutions and disciplinary domains.

- 4.1.8 DRI should support researchers involved in funded research in depositing their data and software outputs in appropriate repositories upon project completion ([Taylor et al. 2022], p. 92). These outputs should include DOIs, clear licensing and count towards professional recognition and career development, e.g. via REF submission ([Taylor et al. 2022], p. 38; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], p. 7; [Durán del Fierro and Littlejohn 2025], p. 8).

- 4.1.9 DRI should support discoverability, access, use/reuse, and interactivity with datasets, including access to data via APIs, direct download, SPARQL, search and visualisation interfaces, and optimisation for search engines, so that research is indexed, visible, and discoverable ([De Roure et al. 2022], pp. 12, 18; [Rodriguez Echavarria et al. 2022]; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.1.10 DRI should support technologies for linking and supporting discoverability by aggregators. Data should be linked across the sector nationally and internationally to unlock research potential ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 11; [Rodriguez Echavarria et al. 2022]; [Black et al. 2024], pp. 9, 11; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 30; [Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], pp. 5, 20; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], p. 14).
- 4.1.11 DRI should establish minimum requirements for data integrity and standardisation, and agree on ontologies, taxonomies, and vocabularies for indexing, naming, and cataloguing. Workflows with Machine learning methods should be explored ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 53; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], p. 14).

Communities have as a key consideration the long-term data preservation of the data.

- 4.1.12 DRI needs to support the long-term preservation of data and software outputs through national and institutional services ([Beavan, Piza, Rob, et al. 2025], p. 8).
- 4.1.13 DRI should offer support at the start of the project regarding standards and guidelines for archiving and preservation that facilitate future data science endeavours, improving accessibility and reducing data wrangling effort; as well as at the end of the project when preparing derived datasets for dissemination ([De Roure et al. 2022], pp. 4, 18).
- 4.1.14 DRI should consider adopting models for digital preservation readiness, such as the NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation or the Digital Preservation Coalition's Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM) ([Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], pp. 4, 21).

Communities have a major concern for the security of the data, given the sensitive nature or other aspects related to curation and use of these datasets.

- 4.1.15 DRI should address security risks and be capable of storing, managing, and providing access to sensitive data ([De Roure et al. 2022]; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5). Trusted Research Environments (TREs) should be available for sensitive data, including historically and commercially sensitive data, as well as stray data. These TREs should have policies tailored to sensitive content rather than a focus on personal data to minimise excessive barriers to research ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 4; [Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], p. 5).
- 4.1.16 DRI should be compliant with defined cybersecurity requirements and provide explicit governance mechanisms ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], pp. 5, 6).
- 4.1.17 The user friction introduced by DRI Cybersecurity approaches on identity management should be reduced when jumping from institutional systems to data and compute resources across the DRI ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 21).

4.2 Research Methods, Workflows and Tools

Communities can benefit from reproducible workflows for data science approaches.

- 4.2.1 DRI should support scalable and reproducible data science and Artificial Intelligence (AI) research workflows, including efficient ways to sort, link, understand, and visualise heterogeneous data in a systematic, configurable, and reproducible manner ([A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 12). In turn, these workflows could significantly accelerate research and promote cumulative data enrichment ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 4; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 43).
- 4.2.2 DRI should provide supported tools and environments for research workflows and pipelines of connected processes and algorithms using virtualisation tools such as virtual machines, Docker, Singularity containers and Kubernetes virtual clusters ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 4). Workflows are likely to migrate between physical infrastructures ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 14).
- 4.2.3 DRI should avoid supplier/vendor lock-in, as it affects hardware and software and requires time and additional cost to rewrite code and migrate ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], pp. 3, 4).

Communities increasingly conduct large-scale analyses that demand computational resources and scalable approaches.

- 4.2.4 DRI should provide easier access to dedicated High-Performance Computing (HPC) systems, scalable cloud services, and processing power to handle large-scale data ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 62; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 72).
- 4.2.5 DRI should provide endpoints and opportunities to generate analysis-ready data for machine learning and to run subsequent analyses at the data provider level (e.g., non-consumptive research/analytics) ([De Roure et al. 2022], pp. 4, 66; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.2.6 DRI needs for monitoring approaches to track metrics, such as CPU usage, project allocations, detailed GPU storage usage, user-facing energy usage, and carbon tracking data ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], pp. 14, 15).
- 4.2.7 DRI needs to mitigate Artificial Intelligence (AI)-related risks, for example, via an ethical governance framework (e.g. an ethics board and in compliance with CARE principles), a human framework for testing and training of algorithms (human-in-the-loop). A training programme to address concerns around the trust and reliability of AI, including its accuracy and data quality, unexplained black-box operations, bias and privacy, should support users to inform their decisions ([Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], p. 4).

Communities predominantly rely on graphical and visually rich interfaces for workflows and interfaces, with limited familiarity with command-line tools and programming languages.

- 4.2.8 DRI should provide an intuitive and visual interface to enable data-intensive research ([Jackson et al. 2023], p. 4), including tailored interfaces for editing, analysis, visualisation/streaming and interaction with data, commentary, citation, as well as extraction ([Rodriguez Echavarria et al. 2022]; [De Roure et al. 2022], p. 44; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5). Accessibility standards should be considered from design stage ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 66; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.2.9 DRI should enable support for interactive/urgent computing interfaces (notebook-style), which are familiar to researchers and software developers within these communities of users ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 4).

Communities favour open science and open data practices.

- 4.2.10 DRI should support open data and open-source cultures and established ways for sharing access to high-quality data with appropriate licensing, interoperability standards and documentation ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 17; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 58; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], pp. 1, 2).
- 4.2.11 DRI should encourage FAIR data principles and Creative Commons open licences with options for a restricted licence if data would otherwise not be ingested ([Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], pp. 4, 21).
- 4.2.12 DRI should promote open research principles tailored to arts and humanities research approaches ([Taylor et al. 2022], p. 51).

Communities want user journeys and use cases for digital methods as a means to support guided access of DRI.

- 4.2.13 DRI should adopt taxonomies, such as the TaDiRAH taxonomy, to categorise popular tasks and guide researchers. DRI should advise on appropriate computing architectures and frameworks for deployment, based on the established requirements of these systems (e.g., data access, CPU/GPU-intensive).
- 4.2.14 DRI should elicit and showcase usable pathfinder projects and demonstrator/pilot applications for popular tasks to support uptake by the community, learning by other people's workflows and overall experiences ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], pp. 3, 9; [Evans et al. 2023], p. 5).
- 4.2.15 DRI should provide a brokerage process or switchboard at the point of access to help users identify the most appropriate resource/federated access and guide users to various components of the infrastructure according to their needs ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 5; [UKRI 2022]). The process should include matching datasets with a suitable repository and guiding users through various computing techniques for data cleaning, text/data mining, data visualisation, immersive technologies, database design, statistics, machine learning, geospatial data, NLP, topic modelling, computer vision, and probabilistic thinking ([UKRI 2022]; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 38).
- 4.2.16 DRI should consider how Artificial Intelligence (AI) methods and Large Language Models (LLMs) can assist researchers in their tasks ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2).
- 4.2.17 DRI should support different levels of use, covering users' varied needs, paired with a clear funding and access model for infrastructure ([Rodriguez Echavarria et al. 2022]; [Black et al. 2024], p. 13)

Communities employ a wide range of research practices and methodologies, including 'living' practices, to produce outputs and datasets. Hence, they carry out a wide range of processes on datasets throughout the research lifecycle.

- 4.2.18 DRI should support a structured and granular approach to versioning, considering both work under development and final outputs, and reflecting on the relationship between changes in

the data and particular actions or methodologies ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 53; [Jackson et al. 2023], p. 4). The UK Registry for the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) and DataCite should be considered, as they already support versioning of DOIs for multiple versions of datasets ([Evans et al. 2023], p. 5).

4.3 Cultures and People

Communities collaborate across institutional boundaries and with non-academic communities at both national and international levels.

- 4.3.1 DRI should allow for authorship of research outputs by individuals and teams across institutions ([Evans et al. 2023], p. 5). Metadata based on existing taxonomies, such as the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT), should be considered.
- 4.3.2 DRI should support access for teams composed of national and international academic and non-academic users, including functionality such as data transfer/migration, permission management, and usage monitoring. Copyright and licensing of DRI-related resources should support agreements among multiple institutions ([De Roure et al. 2022]; [Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], p. 5). Collaboration can be enabled via 'short-lived collaborations' and 'virtual organisations' that bring together staff from multiple institutions, often in different countries ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 7).
- 4.3.3 DRI should consider reusable tools and approaches to share a minimum set of information about a researcher, including authentication protocols and identifiers (e.g. ORCID) ([Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 6).
- 4.3.4 DRI should encourage cross-disciplinary national and international collaborations through community engagement activities, such as hackathons ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 4; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2; [Romanova et al. 2021], p. 15; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023]). These activities should promote collaboration among various professional roles, including digital Research Technical Professionals, encompassing Research Software Engineers (RSEs), data scientists and other researchers ([DisCouRSE: Developing a Community of Leaders 2026]; [Step-up Project 2026],[De Roure et al. 2022], p. 8,[Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 30), as well as with other sectors such as the creative industries ([Romanova et al. 2021]).

Communities benefit from active connection, nurturing, as well as inclusive and sustained growth.

- 4.3.5 DRI should develop and sustain inclusive communities of practice beyond disciplinary domains, such as History, Language, Digital Humanities and Archaeology and academic audiences ([Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]; [Taylor et al. 2022], pp. 10, 26) and across diverse epistemic cultures ([Durán del Fierro and Littlejohn 2025]).
- 4.3.6 DRI should be supported by networking, approaches for collaborating, skills, formal and informal training, internships, and placements to support people at various career stages and in different organisations ([De Roure et al. 2022], pp. 17, 72; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2; [Romanova et al. 2021], pp. 20, 21; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], pp. 34, 35; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 47;[Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]).

4.3.7 DRI should invest long-term and sustainably in capacity, training and bridging digital literacy divides, especially boosting skills in digital methods and technologies ([De Roure et al. 2022], pp. 4, 11; [Black et al. 2024], p. 10; [Collier and Hamilton 2025], p. 22; [Evans et al. 2023], p. 6; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 73; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], pp. 12, 27; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], p. 7; [Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]). Environmental awareness for doing digital research should also be considered ([A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 28; [Evans et al. 2023], p. 6).

Communities consider digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs) to be key stakeholders to expand access to DRI.

4.3.8 DRI should ensure continuous equitable collaboration with dRTPs, including dedicated and one-to-one 'clinic' style support ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 48; [Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 8; [Black et al. 2024], p. 10; [Romanova et al. 2021], p. 17; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 12; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 33; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], pp. 1, 2; [Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]).

4.3.9 DRI should leverage community managers to broker access to dRTPs/RSEs and widen engagement with DRI ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 10; [Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]).

4.3.10 DRI should ensure broader availability of dRTP roles ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarria, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 2; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], pp. 48, 73; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 10; [Beavan, Piza, Gillespie, et al. 2025]).

Communities see professional development across roles as essential to realising the full potential of DRI.

4.3.11 DRI should invest in the human aspect to make infrastructure viable, including widening opportunities for individuals with clear progression paths, funding beyond projects and improved salaries, as well as career development opportunities ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 71; [Romanova et al. 2021], pp. 13, 14; [A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 8; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 33; [Durán del Fierro and Littlejohn 2025]).

Communities consider the evaluation frameworks, particularly the Research Excellence Framework (REF), as crucial in shaping researchers' careers.

4.3.12 DRI should support submissions to national evaluation frameworks, including framing data and software as outputs and allowing for the documentation of the research journeys ([Jackson et al. 2023], p. 4; [Sufi, Emily Bell, and A.-M. Sichani 2023], p. 71; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 41).

4.3.13 DRI should provide portable access to its infrastructure and allow researchers' outputs to be portable. Policies should be flexible to accommodate staff mobility ([Taylor et al. 2022], p. 37) as researchers transition between academia, independent research organisations (IROs), and other sectors, often early in their careers.

4.3.14 DRI should allow for software produced during research to be accessed as a research output, with software citation and reproducibility underpinning impact metrics ([A.-M. Sichani et al. 2023], p. 7).

Sustainability, in its various forms, is a central priority for the community.

- 4.3.15 DRI should define sustainability in terms of environmental, labour, and collaboration practices ([Ross et al. 2024], p. 1).
- 4.3.16 DRI should monitor the environmental impact of infrastructure with a long-term aim of carbon neutrality, where achievable and considering the risks of exacerbating unsustainable resource consumption ([Eamonn Bell, Rodriguez Echavarría, and Thiyagalingam 2025], p. 7; [Black et al. 2024], p. 13; [Ross et al. 2024], p. 29; [Zwiggelaar, R. et al. 2022], p. 21; [Hawkins and A. M. Sichani 2024], p. 2).
- 4.3.17 DRI should consider different funding scenarios and strike an equitable balance, aware of power asymmetries, for example, that larger organisations usually attract bigger funding ([Romanova et al. 2021], p. 21; [Durán del Fierro and Littlejohn 2025]). DRI should consider supporting users post-project completion ([De Roure et al. 2022], p. 14; [Taylor et al. 2022], p. 41).
- 4.3.18 DRI should reflect upon the success and failure of previous infrastructure to develop future strategies successfully ([Romanova et al. 2021], p. 21).

5 Requirements for Data Federation: Insights from the Data Services

A series of interviews with representatives of *six* data services, mostly funded by AHRC, was conducted to examine data service providers' perspectives. The services interviewed were the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo); the Archaeology Data Service (ADS); the Literary and Linguistic Data Service (LLDS); the British Library Research Repository; the Museum Data Service (MDS); the Heritage Science Data Service (HSDS). At the time of the research, the Enact Practice Research Data Service had not yet been materialised; hence, it was not included in the sample. The interviews focused on exploring the nature of the data in each data service, data practices within their associated communities, as well as challenges, opportunities and aspirations for a federated infrastructure environment. The analysis of the interviews was structured around the main themes which were also employed in the interview sections (see Appendix 8), while allowing for subthemes to emerge. The findings from these interviews are presented below.

5.1 Data types and formats

The interviews confirmed that there is significant heterogeneity in data types, formats, sizes, and data management practices across services (requirement 4.1.1). Data types currently supported by data services can include images, media, 3D, GIS shapefiles, geophysics data, LIDAR, volumetric data and genomic sequences. While most services host primary assets, others aggregate metadata from institutions, such as Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums (GLAM). A common narrative across all services is the increase in data, specifically from commercial infrastructure projects (e.g., archaeological digs) or large-scale digitisation projects.

5.2 FAIR data practices

While good practices can be found at the data-service level regarding FAIR practices, further technical coordination across data services is required to meet requirements for discoverability (requirements 4.1.9 and 4.1.10).

Building on strong expertise in data curation, the data services employ domain-specific metadata schemas, e.g., the Darwin Core for natural history data, the Monument Inventory Data Standard

(MIDAS), and the Spectrum for museum data, and there is a desire to move towards the use of standardised ontologies (requirement 4.1.11). DOIs are the standard for datasets across data services, yet some services report a lack of a citation culture.

Data services encourage the use of open licenses, such as CC-BY and CC0, to facilitate reuse (requirement 4.2.11). Deposit agreements allow data services to distribute data rather than transfer the copyright, ensuring the depositor retains ownership. Where an agreement is unavailable, the institution must own the copyright to grant a license, which is not practical in all cases.

When providing access to data beyond licensing restrictions, the primary sensitivities include legal considerations, such as the Legal Deposit Libraries (Non-Print Works) Regulations 2013, the Data Protection Acts, and the Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988 (CDPA). The implication is that access should be confined to controlled environments and used only for permitted purposes as identified in requirements 4.1.3 and 4.1.4. For instance, one of the data services is exploring the use of physical walled-off sections of reading rooms to provide secure access to restricted data, though remote access remains legally difficult. There is wide interest in the potential of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to enable controlled access to sensitive or copyrighted data (requirement 4.1.15).

There is evidence of versioning approaches (see requirement 4.2.18), including support for versioning records, linking new versions to old ones and allowing researchers to cite specific iterations of data used in citations. For instance, *living records* or continuous updates are a hallmark of biological data (e.g., re-identifying a species) in data infrastructure. Moreover, versioning is considered a core requirement for some of the data services going forward.

5.3 Access and connectivity

A common model for access across data services is *Search and Download*. Bulk exports/downloads can be provided by data services, often through scripts or long lists of URLs. However, moving large-scale data to external compute facilities can be a major bottleneck in most cases (requirement 4.1.6).

In addition, most data services allow for programmatic access to metadata via the HTTP-based Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). Some, such as the ADS and DiSSCo, provide additional REST APIs for access. Often, API rate limits are used. While there is some positive views on enabling data-crawling and batch analysis, the impact on the infrastructure needs to be mitigated. A significant concern is the impact of unregulated AI bots crawling repositories and straining infrastructure. Hence, considerations regarding governance, cybersecurity (requirement 4.1.16) and ensuring local servers cope with demand need to be taken aboard.

Various projects have explored Artificial Intelligence workflows for data mining and metadata enhancement. For instance, computer vision models are used for automated species identification from images, and NLP is used to transcribe millions of handwritten specimen labels. These workflows facilitate linking specimens to collectors, publications, and DNA sequences (requirement 4.2.1). While most data services are using AI for this type of *back-room* tasks, formal AI policies are required, as these are largely absent or tethered to broader university statements (requirement 4.2.7).

Overall, there is a keen interest in a federated interface between data and compute infrastructures to allow users to move/use data into their own software environments (requirements 4.2.4 and 4.2.5).

Moreover, there is a strong interest in federated Identity and Authentication Management (IAM) (requirement 4.3.3). Currently, only one data service uses a federated Shibboleth model, while other services rely on institutional accounts or IP-based access within an institution. There was strong interest in providing authenticated user functionality, such as API access, cross-search of sensitive metadata, and access to Virtual Research Environments (VREs).

5.4 Challenges, Opportunities and Impact

Certifications (e.g., CoreTrustSeal) and long-term sustainability (see requirement 4.1.2) are considered positive stories, while enabling access, large-scale aggregation, and the reuse of data are often desired impacts. For data services, ongoing challenges include sustainably maintaining the infrastructure, long-term preservation and protecting against cybersecurity threats (requirement 4.1.15).

A universal *pain point* is the difficulty of recruiting and retaining digital Research Technical Professionals (requirement 4.3.11). The data services cannot compete with private-sector salaries and they rely on dRTPs within HEIs, where grading systems often pose barriers to hiring dRTPs.

5.5 Federation Aspirations

In terms of federation, there is strong support for a suite of UKDRI national services rather than a single, monolithic platform. Priorities for data services include improved search and discoverability, shared AI infrastructure (e.g., public Large Language Model Infrastructure for research), and improved connectivity between compute and data (requirement 4.2.4). Distribution of technical infrastructure, such as off-site distributed long-term storage and backups, to improve preservation, disaster and cybersecurity resilience is seen as a potential area of coordination in a federated ecosystem (requirement 4.1.16). In particular, there was a strong note that a level of security and *arms-length* protection could be provided through federation, compared to what an individual institution can achieve on its own.

6 Requirements for enabling discoverability across data services: Insights from prototype development

Further work was conducted to identify the specific requirements for infrastructures and platforms to improve discoverability across a federated data ecosystem. This further work directly addressed the needs identified by research communities and data service providers to improve how research is indexed, visible, and discoverable (requirements 4.1.9, 4.1.10, and 4.1.11). For this, a proof-of-concept prototype was designed and prototyped, testing various requirements identified during the interviews, in particular searching across multiple services from a single query and linking discovered data with compute power. To close the loop from discovery to reference, the proof of concept explored the use of a dedicated citation component which can assemble a formatted reference list directly from a federated result set.

The development of the prototype was an iterative, attritional process of discovery, building out organically from a small set of core functions. At its simplest, the interface provides the ability to take a single argument — a text string or an integer — that can be passed consistently to a range of providers, satisfying the minimal requirements for a search query (string), a result limit (numeric), and an API key, where required (string). Once those core functions were established, the development effort concentrated on adding research value to that baseline, prioritised by the recurrent themes from our interviews with the data services and by their idiosyncrasies. It further prioritised partly inferred usability concerns drawn from the project team's experience running workshops.

6.1 Lessons learned

The development evidenced that:

- 6.1.1 Building on available expertise within the data services, single sign-on across the A&H landscape represents the most concrete requirement the roadmap can address.

- 6.1.2 Standardising API access configured for direct access from external applications is required. Standardised metadata is key for federation. APIs and Search parameters vary across services. Yet, given the discipline-specific nature of the metadata, a fully federated search across all data services might not always make sense.
- 6.1.3 Sanctioned mechanisms (e.g., known IP ranges, attested clients, or codified request rate-limit norms) for programmatic access can be the means by which research consumers are distinguished from harvesting bots.
- 6.1.4 Identifiers below the dataset level remain inconsistent. Without item-level identifiers minted at source, every application has to solve the same disambiguation problem independently, rather than relying on an identifier that does it once for everyone.
- 6.1.5 Beyond inspection and harmonisation, operations that add research value to the records include *filtering and transformation, reconciliation, linking and entity-resolution, as well as inference through AI models*.
- 6.1.6 Pagination is limited even on most accessible services, which currently limits the potential for bulk extraction at the scale required by data services.

The requirements, recommendations, and proof-of-concept exercise were disseminated at the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association Annual Event 2026. *[feedback to be added]*

This work for the federation roadmap implies that improving discoverability across a federated data ecosystem requires a coordinated effort. A commons-style effort with a shared contract and maintenance burden could support federated access and discovery. It aligns incentives — the party that benefits from being discoverable maintains sovereignty over the means of discovery. A shared, published specification with an agreed-upon, simple description of input, outputs, and the format the data must follow will enable any team — including the data services themselves — to build ways to expose data for their own service without needing to understand the rest of the application. The specification need not be complex; the value lies in its existence and stability.

7 Recommendations

Our understanding of the DRI landscape in the Arts and Humanities and the following recommendations are informed by the activities described above: literature review, conducting interviews with data services, trailing approaches for visual interfaces, shaping and delivering the DISKAH fellowship programme with A&H researchers, and engaging in various outreach and dissemination opportunities at national and international levels.

All these have been distilled into valuable insights and lessons learned, which, in turn, can inform DRI directions to address the community's requirements for compute- and data-intensive research and practice. The following recommendations are organised according to the four key components of a federated compute stack, serving the requirements for the A&H communities. These components are illustrated in Figure 1, and include: 1) Infrastructure, Platforms & Tools (***IPT***); 2) Data (***DAT***); 3) Access by Communities & Skills Capacity (***ACC***); and 4) Policy (***POL***). Each recommendation is provided with a perceived priority from the community, and an owner within the UKRI-DRI ecosystem, including a) the funder, e.g. UKRI and DSIT (***funder***); b) governance and advisory bodies, e.g. DRI advisory board and research councils (***governance bodies***); c) DRI ecosystem, e.g. Next National Supercomputing Service (NNSS), AI Research Resource (AIRR), and National Compute Resources

(NCRs) (**DRI-compute services**) and data services (DRI-data services); and d) the community of A&H networks (**Communities**).

Figure 1: Diagram of a federated compute stack for the Arts and Humanities

7.1 Infrastructure, Platforms & Tools (IPT)

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-IPT-01	Provide standardised, interactive notebook interfaces (e.g. Jupyter) and other low-barrier front-ends that researchers can use without command-line skills.	Must have	DRI-compute services
A&H-IPT-02	Provide Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for working with sensitive or access-restricted material.	Must have	DRI-compute services
A&H-IPT-03	Provide workflow platforms (e.g. Galaxy) and <i>data playgrounds</i> that enable researchers to build reproducible, shareable analysis pipelines.	Must have	DRI-compute services
A&H-IPT-04	Provide shared research-cloud infrastructure through open, publicly governed science cloud platforms — such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) — built on open standards and federation in preference to relying solely on proprietary commercial cloud services, so that compute, storage, and services can be accessed, shared, and reused across institutions, rather than siloed locally or locked into a single vendor.	Must have	DRI-compute services
A&H-IPT-05	Provide access to AI models for inference to support large-scale data analysis.	Should have	DRI-compute services

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-IPT-06	Provide access to agentic coding assistants to support software and workflow development.	Should have	DRI-compute services

7.2 Data (DAT)

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-DAT-01	Provide documented and standardised programmatic access so that compute environments, analysis platforms, and tools can connect to the service directly, enabling AI workflows, data access, and data sharing without manual data transfer.	Must have	DRI-data services
A&H-DAT-02	Establish a technically oriented coordination board for A&H data services to ensure consistency across services — covering metadata integrity, harmonisation of ontologies, taxonomies and vocabularies across domain schemas, API access, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), provenance pathways, and citation generation — so as to improve research integrity and the discoverability of data.	Must have	DRI-data services
A&H-DAT-03	Provide distributed, long-term storage with backups across A&H data services to strengthen preservation and disaster- and cybersecurity-resilience.	Must have	DRI-data services
A&H-DAT-04	Implement Identity and Access Management (IAM) to enable secure, federated access across A&H data repositories.	Must have	DRI-data services

7.3 Communities & Skills Capacity (Access) (ACC)

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-ACC-01	Develop a Community Centre of Excellence (CCE) in Arts and Humanities (A&H) to interface access to Infrastructures, Platforms and Tools.	Must have	Community
A&H-ACC-02	Broker access to Digital Research Technical Professionals to support optimising code and workflows, overcoming technical difficulties, and navigating unfamiliar infrastructure.	Must have	Community

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-ACC-03	Implement capacity-building and skills development on the use of DRI ecosystems — through train-the-trainer approaches, peer-to-peer knowledge exchange, dissemination of training, and showcasing of use cases — to drive uptake.	Must have	Community
A&H-ACC-04	Develop a coordinated case for participation; on that basis, the funder should commit funding to strategically join the relevant European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) in A&H disciplines — Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN), Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH), and European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS).	Must have	Community and Funder
A&H-ACC-05	Commission a scoping study for a UK consortium of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research infrastructures. The study should map the existing ecosystem of services, data, and tools across SSH disciplines, identify the key stakeholders and current initiatives, assess options for governance and funding, and set out a phased roadmap and business case for bringing them together to reduce duplication, improve interoperability, and drive innovation.	Should have	Community

7.4 Policy

ID	Recommendation	Priority	Owner
A&H-POL-01	Develop policies and support mechanisms that recognise and accommodate non-linear, iterative, and flexible modes of working with data and digital methods, rather than assuming linear project lifecycles through flexible funding conditions, reporting timelines, and research-assessment criteria that value iterative and exploratory work.	Must have	Governance bodies
A&H-POL-02	Scope the participation and contribution models by which researchers and institutions can join and help sustain a federated infrastructure — for example, membership tiers, resource or in-kind contributions, and funding commitments.	Must have	Governance bodies

A&H-POL-03	Scope a tiered readiness framework against which infrastructure components can self-assess and signal how far their technical capabilities and policies meet the federation's priorities — i.e. defined readiness levels, each with clear criteria.	Must have	Governance bodies
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8 Appendix A: Interview questions

Our aim is to collectively elicit requirements around federation within the current Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Arts and Humanities landscape to contribute to the NFCS roadmap development.

You will be asked to respond to the interview questions included in this document. The interview is expected to last for 60-90 minutes. All interviews will be recorded and then transcribed to facilitate analysis.

Data Characteristics and Scale

8.0.1 What types of data are you hosting in your data DRI service and in what formats?

8.0.2 What is the volume of data that you are hosting?

FAIR Data Practices and Stewardship

8.0.3 Do you host sensitive data, and can these be accessed within your data service?

8.0.4 Do you accommodate various versions or updates of the data that you are hosting?

8.0.5 Are there any specific metadata schemas that your data service uses?

8.0.6 Do you support or mint PIDs in your data service (and which form) to facilitate data interoperability?

8.0.7 Which licences does your service apply to data?

Programmatic Access and Connectivity

8.0.8 Could access be arranged to export data from your service to an unspecified group of researchers, e.g. to a national compute facility or A&H focused workshop?

8.0.9 Do you currently provide programmatic access to your data (e.g. REST API, SPARQL) and do you have any insights into the digital workflows that this access enables?

8.0.10 Which identity and authentication methods do you use for enabling access to data?

8.0.11 Can the data service users run automated, batch analyses using your APIs, and would you allow them to if not already implemented?

8.0.12 Does your data service have an AI strategy and/or policy?

Research Impact

8.0.13 What are your achievements in making data accessible? Are there any challenges that your users encounter when storing, accessing or sharing data (e.g. cost, volume, technical issues, copyright/licencing)?

Technical Infrastructure and Federation Aspirations

- 8.0.14 Can you describe the infrastructure that underpins your data service? (i.e. scale of storage and compute, hosting, backup management, funding, human resources to maintain)
- 8.0.15 If there were national services that could replace any of the technology components discussed above (e.g. a distributed backed-up storage platform with backups), would you have leveraged it or considered migrating to it? Please explain your priorities in terms of the most useful services.

References

- Beavan, David, Andre Piza, Stuart Gillespie, Cyara Buchuck-Wilsenach, Claire Bailey-Ross, Bickford Jake, Edward Chalstrey, Mary Chester-Kadwell, Neil Chue Hong, Arianna Ciula, Jonathan Cooper, Tom J Couch, Dietz Sarah, Fagan Stephanie, Pieter Francois, Dr Eirini Goudarouli, Neil Grindley, Felicity Guest, Timothy Hobson, Natasha Kitcher, Paola Marchionni, Katherine McDonough, Pamela Mellen, Nicola Osborne, Lisa Otty, Mark Parsons, Michael Pidd, Clementina Ramirez-Marengo, Rowlands Emma, Oscar Seip, Anna-Maria Sichani, Thomas Storrar, Melissa Terras, Charlotte Tupman, Marion Weinzierl, and Kalle Westerling (Mar. 2025). *Towards a National Research Software Engineering Capability in Arts and Humanities Research: a Roadmap*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15083396](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083396). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083396> (cit. on pp. 2, 7, 8).
- Beavan, David, Andre Piza, Hearn Rob, Fagan Stephanie, Pieter Francois, and Rowlands Emma (Mar. 2025). *Evidencing the Impact of Research Software Engineers on Arts & Humanities Scholarship*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15083632](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083632). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083632> (cit. on pp. 2, 4).
- Bell, Eamonn, Karina Rodriguez Echavarria, and Jeyan Thiyaalingam (Sept. 2025). *CCP-AHC Roadmap Open Draft*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17099176](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17099176). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17099176> (cit. on pp. 1–3, 5–9).
- Black, Suzanne R., Rosa Filgueira, Lesley McAra, Brendan Miles, Mark Parsons, and Melissa Terras (2024). “Cultural analytics in the UK: events data potential for the creative and cultural industries”. In: *Cultural Trends* 33.5, pp. 680–695. DOI: [10.1080/09548963.2023.2263378](https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2023.2263378). eprint: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2023.2263378>. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2023.2263378> (cit. on pp. 2, 4, 6, 8, 9).
- Collier, I. and M. Hamilton (Sept. 2025). “UKRI DRI AAAI Workshop”. Internal report, unpublished (cit. on pp. 2–5, 7, 8).
- De Roure, David, John Moore, Kevin Page, Toby Burrows, David Beavan, Timothy Hobson, Giles Bergel, Abhishek Dutta, Andrew Zisserman, Aruna Bhaugeerutty, Samantha Blickhan, Alan Chamberlain, Arianna Ciula, Ian Cooke, Stella Wisdom, Graeme Hawley, Tim Crawford, Golnaz Badkobeh, David Lewis, Alistair Porter, Laurent Pugin, Rodolfo Zitellini, Nicholas Cronk, Birgit Mikus, Neil Jefferies, Peter Cornwell, Huw Jones, Christopher Melen, Kieron Niven, Rachel Proudfoot, Gethin Rees, Pedro Máximo Rocha, Amy Sampson, Martin Wynne, Nicola Barnet, Masud Khokar, and John Salter (Aug. 2022). *DigiSpec: Scoping Future Born-Digital Data Services for the Arts and Humanities: Case Reports*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4716148](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4716148). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4716148> (cit. on pp. 2–9).
- DisCourSE: Developing a Community of Leaders (2026). <https://discourse-network.github.io/>. URL: <https://discourse-network.github.io/> (cit. on p. 7).
- Durán del Fierro, Francisco and Allison Littlejohn (Nov. 2025). *Inclusive Futures of Federated Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI). A Scoping Review of Cultural Challenges to Federation*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17641455](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17641455). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17641455> (cit. on pp. 3, 7–9).
- Evans, Jenny, Adam Vials Moore, Helen Bailey, Jenny Basford, Rachael Kotarski, Joshua Mead, Holly Ranger, Alan Stone, Nina Watts, and Neal White (June 2023). *Practice Research Voices (PRVOICES): Final report and recommendations*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34737/w3803>. URL: <https://westminsterresearch.westminster.ac.uk/item/w3803/practice-research-voices-prvoices-final-report-and-recommendations> (cit. on pp. 2, 6–8).
- Hawkins, Ashleigh and Anna Maria Sichani (Oct. 2024). ‘Data Matters’: Report on the Towards a National Collection Discovery Projects focus group on data management, documentation, and

- archiving practices in digital cultural heritage projects*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14006955](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006955). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006955> (cit. on pp. 2–4, 6, 8, 9).
- Jackson, T., C. Knowles, S. McLaughlin, R. Kotarski, A. De Little, M. Warren, and A. Horne (Sept. 2023). *Sustaining Practice Assets for Research, Knowledge, Learning and Engagement (SPARKLE) : Final Report and Recommendations*. Report 10.48785/100/296. This report is an open access publication distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution license (CC-BY 4.0). ARRAY(0x56113b0c5988). URL: <https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/id/eprint/203045/> (cit. on pp. 2–5, 7, 8).
- McGillivray, Barbara, Beatrice Alex, Sarah Ames, Guyda Armstrong, David Beavan, Arianna Ciula, Giovanni Colavizza, James Cummings, David De Roure, Adam Farquhar, Simon Hengchen, Anouk Lang, James Loxley, Eirini Goudarouli, Federico Nanni, Andrea Nini, Julianne Nyhan, Nicola Osborne, Thierry Poibeau, Mia Ridge, Sonia Ranade, James Smithies, Melissa Terras, Andreas Vlachidis, and Pip Willcox (Aug. 2020). “The challenges and prospects of the intersection of humanities and data science: A White Paper from The Alan Turing Institute”. In: DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.12732164.v5](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12732164.v5). URL: https://figshare.com/articles/online_resource/The_challenges_and_prospects_of_the_intersection_of_humanities_and_data_science_A_White_Paper_from_The_Alan_Turing_Institute/12732164 (cit. on p. 2).
- Rodriguez Echavarría, Karina, Myrsini Samaroudi, Neil Jakeman, Mark Hedges, Xavier Aure Calvet, Tim Weyrich, Ronald Haynes, Douglas Boyer, Julie Winchester, Mackenzie Shepard, and Silverton Edward (Nov. 2022). *Report on the Development of a Multidimensional Data Service for the Arts and Humanities*. Version v0. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18349293](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18349293). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18349293> (cit. on pp. 2–6).
- Romanova, Natasha, Arianna Ciula, James Smithies, Neil Jakeman, Órla Murphy, Charlotte Tupman, Jane Winters, Jennifer Edmond, Michelle Doran, Paul Gooding, Lorna Hughes, Patricia Murrieta-Flores, and Justin Tonra (July 2021). *Capacity Enhancement in Digital Humanities in the United Kingdom and Ireland: Training and Beyond*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5105938](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105938). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105938> (cit. on pp. 2, 3, 7–9).
- Ross, Jen, Philippa Sheail, Melissa Terras, and Cate Schofield (Sept. 2024). *Infrastructure Futures for Digital Cultural Heritage*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.13710266](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710266). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13710266> (cit. on pp. 2, 9).
- Sichani, Anna-Maria, Ruth Ahnert, James Baker, David Beavan, Arianna Ciula, Stephen Crouch, David De Roure, Pieter Francois, James Hetherington, Neil Jeffries, Barbara McGillivray, Mia Ridge, Melissa Terras, Charlotte Tupman, Mark Turner, Marion Weinzierl, Pip Willcox, Jane Winters, Martin Wynne, and James Smithies (July 2023). *iDAH Research Software Engineering (RSE) Steering Group Working Paper*. Version v.1.0. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8177926](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8177926). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8177926> (cit. on pp. 2, 5, 7, 8).
- Step-up Project (2026). *CONNECTED: Connecting trusted Arts and Humanities data repositories*. URL: <https://step-up.ac.uk/drtp/> (cit. on p. 7).
- Sufi, Shoaib, Emily Bell, and Anna-Maria Sichani (Feb. 2023). *Report on the AHRC Digital/ Software Requirements Survey 2021: Where is Investment Needed?* Version 1.0. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7686348](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686348). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686348> (cit. on pp. 2, 3, 5–8).
- Taylor, Rebecca, Johanna Walker, Simon Hettrick, Philippa Broadbent, and David De Roure (Oct. 2022). *Shaping Data and Software Policy in the Arts and Humanities Research Community: A Study for the AHRC*. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10518740](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10518740). URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10518740> (cit. on pp. 2–4, 6–9).
- UKRI (2022). *CONNECTED: Connecting trusted Arts and Humanities data repositories*. URL: <https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=AH%2FW00755X%2F1#/tabOverview> (cit. on pp. 2, 6).

Zwiggelaar, R. et al. (Nov. 2022). “AHRC iDAH Project Report, Towards a National AI-Enabled Repository for Wales, Development Grant AH/W007487/1”. Internal report, unpublished (cit. on pp. [2](#), [4–7](#), [9](#)).